

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Mamatova Zulfizar

**THE NEED FOR DIAGNOSTIC AND CORRECTION OF ANTI-SOCIAL
BEHAVIOR IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS**

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2023/IYUN

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